

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Review Article

**STUDYING JOB INVOLVEMENT AND ITS RELATION WITH
OTHER VARIABLES AMONG NON-FACULTY STAFF OF
IRANIAN UNIVERSITIES OF MEDICAL SCIENCES: A REVIEW****Abdolreza Gilavand¹ and Mohsen Mohammadbidaghi^{*2}**¹Department of Education Development Center, Ahvaz Jundishapur University of Medical Sciences, Ahvaz, Iran²Department of Education Development Center, Dezful University of Medical Sciences, Dezful, Iran**Abstract:**

Introduction: Considering the effective role of job involvement in increasing organizational effectiveness, this research has been done to investigate job involvement and its relation with other variables among non-faculty staff of Iranian universities of medical sciences.

Materials and Methods: This has been done as a simple overview in 2018. Research data was collected through the search of published articles in Internet sources and valid scientific databases, with searching 3 words "job involvement, staff and Iran", without linguistic and temporal limitation.

Results: With investigating 9 conducted researches in health educational centers affiliated with the Ministry of Health of Iran, this research has come to the conclusion that job involvement has direct and positive relationship with such variables as "Strategic Alignment", "Servant Leadership", "Transformational Leadership", "Demographic Characteristics", "Organizational Culture", "Strategic Alignment and Valuable Work", "Role of Professional Ethics" and "Emotional Intelligence".

Discussion and Conclusion: job involvement will occur when in an organization the staff act with more than their job expectations and communicate mentally, emotionally and physically with their work. Job involvement will have consequences such as increasing the positive attitude of the work environment, improving mental health of the employees, and promoting their performance and behavior in the organization. Therefore, it is necessary to strengthen it and other related variables in organizations.

Keywords: *Job involvement, Iranian University of Medical Sciences.*

Corresponding author:*Mohsen Mohammadbidaghi,**Department of Education Development Center,
Dezful University of Medical Sciences, Dezful, IranEmail: mohsenmb57@yahoo.com

QR code

Please cite this article in press: Gilavand A, Mohammadbidaghi. M, *studying Job Involvement and Its Relation to Other Variables in Iranian Universities of Medical Sciences: a Review*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2018; 05(03)

INTRODUCTION:

Human resources are among the factors that are very effective in the survival of organizations and attract always the attention of the officials and managers of the organizations. Studying and reviewing the history of the development and transformation of industrial societies shows that skilled and trained human resources had an undeniable effect in the process of transformation of traditional society to the industrial one. So human resource is the most important and the most original factor in the development of societies and organizations. It was once thought that meeting the needs of individuals would reduce the resources and facilities of organizations. Based on this conception, for reaching the minimum return we need to meet the minimum requirements, but nowadays, this theory has been completely ruled out (1). Management experts now believe that the return in organizations is reduced if the actual needs of employees are not properly understood and the managers do not seek to satisfy them, because their positive interest in their jobs makes more effort and therefore reduces costs (2). Human being is based on multiple needs. Each of the human needs at a certain time provides the ground for action and reaction to different situations and conditions. In other words, each human need has a motivational force that, if enabled, can direct human behavior in a particular direction (3). Employees working in health centers are always exposed to the risk of infectious diseases, due to their specific clinical environment and direct relationship with patients (4-5). Every year, many elites in order To continue studying as well as to recruit as faculty members enter the universities of medical sciences in Iran (6-7-8). Studies have shown that the performance of the medical sciences universities of Iran has led to the empowerment of patients through the implementation of the health promotion plan (9).

The term involvement in the dictionary has been translated into various meanings such as, candidacy, commitment, engagement, employment. Cohen (1990) was the first to introduce the concept of job involvement to HRM texts. In his view, involving in work is a kind of psychological state that brings the individuals' self-existence under domination of their own working roles. He identified three dimensions for job involvement, namely Vigor, Dedication and Absorption; the vigor refers to person's inclination to apply high energy levels, and effort, as well as endurance during work. Dedication is deep attachment to work and sense of importance, passion and challenge in work. Absorption means intense

intellectual concentration in work along with satisfaction and feeling of happiness. After Cohen numerous researches were conducted to define, identify dimensions and operationalize job involvement. The findings of most of these scholars have much in common. For example, Schufflee and Bucker identified three energetic, affective, and cognitive dimensions for job involvement, which are similar, respectively, with the dimensions of rigor, dedication and absorption in the model of Cohen. In the social science literature, the root of this concept comes from the theory of role and, in particular, the works of Irwin Goffman (1960). Goffman believes that individuals in the society accept various roles; he defines involvement in a role as "self-inspired attachment to the role and great attention and effort for implementing it" (10).

Job involvement refers to the degree to which individuals find psychologically identity in their current job (11). High job involvement is a desirable feature. People with high job involvement are satisfied with their job, show a positive attitude to work and express a high commitment to the organization and their colleagues (12); such people rarely think of leaving their jobs and are expected to work for your organization during years. Job involvement is associated positively with variables such as organizational commitment, organizational citizenship behavior, motivation and performance and negatively with absence and turnover (13). At the same time, some believe that most research on job involvement has been realized in large organizations (14). In this sense, little attention has been paid to this in other areas, especially educational and health centers. Therefore, this research is a simple overview to investigate job involvement and its relationship with other variables in hospitals and educational centers affiliated to Iranian universities of medical sciences.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This study was a simple overview conducted in 2018 to investigate job involvement and its relationship with other variables in hospitals and educational centers affiliated to Iranian universities of medical sciences. Research data was collected through the search of published articles in Internet sources and valid scientific databases (SID, MAGIRAN, PubMed, Scopus and Web of Science), with searching 3 words "job involvement, staff and Iran", without linguistic and temporal limitation. In the initial search, 21 related studies were found, of which 9 researches that were completely related were used in this research.

RESULTS:

In hospitals and educational centers affiliated to Iranian Universities of Medical Sciences, several studies have been done on job involvement and its relation with variables such as ("Strategic Alignment", "Servant Leadership", "Transformational Leadership", "Demographic Characteristics", "Organizational Culture", "Strategic Alignment and Valuable Work", "Role of Professional Ethics" and "Emotional Intelligence"). Here are 9 examples:

Gorgi et al conducted a research entitled "relationship between strategic adjustment and job involvement in Hashemi Nejad Hospital in Tehran". The population of this study included 424 people of nursing, administrative, financial, support and paramedical classes in Hashemi Nejad Hospital in Tehran; from these 202 people were selected as sample size. A questionnaire was used to collect data. Based on the findings, the mean scores and standard deviation of strategic adaptation and job involvement were 31.4 ± 90.47 from 40 and 54.19 ± 7.34 from 70, respectively. Also, the results of linear regression analysis showed that strategic adjustment could be a predicting variable for job involvement. They conclude that strategic adjustment is one of the factors affecting employees' job involvement, as well as the targeting is based on individual and environmental conditions, developing strategies to direct employees for achieving goals, participative targeting and accurate and transparent information to employees; they are some effective ways of improving the strategic adjustment and consequently job involvement (14).

In a research, Khalesi et al studied "Relationship between Servant Leadership and Its Quadruple Dimensions with Job Involvement among Employees of Health and Educational Centers in Kurdistan University of Medical Sciences". The statistical sample of this research included 151 personnel working in these centers. Data were collected using a questionnaire of servant leadership and a job involvement questionnaire. The results of this research showed that there is a significant and positive relationship between servant leadership and its four dimensions (service, humility, trustworthiness, confidence and kindness) on the one hand and employees' job involvement on the other; the servant leadership and job involvement were moderate. They concluded in the end that, in order to enhance the level of servant leadership, the managers should always pioneer in the serving others, both inside and outside the organization, and consider the service to be as their duties (15).

Bahrami et al conducted a research entitled "Investigating the Relationship between Transformational Leadership Dimensions and Job Involvement of Employees from the Viewpoints of Managers in Educational Hospitals of Yazd in 2013". The population of this research included all (excellent, middle, operational) managers, educational hospitals (Shahid Sadoughi, Rahnemoun, Afshar, Accidents and burns) affiliated to Yazd University of Medical Sciences. Because of limited research population, 180 people of the statistical population were selected as the sample. Data were collected by Transformational Leadership Questionnaire from the perspective of Bass & Elio Managers as well as Thomas Job Involvement Inventory. The results of this research showed that there is a positive and significant relationship between the transformational leadership and its four dimensions (mental stimulation, inspirational motivation, ideal influence, individual considerations) on the one hand and job involvement in four hospitals with $r = 289$ and $p = 0.01$. They concluded in the end that the transforming leader of hospitals would create positive changes in the performance of the staff to do better work, to enhance their learning and increase their ability (16).

Saeed et al conducted a research entitled "Relationship between Job Involvement and Demographic Characteristics in Nurses of Selected Hospitals in Tehran and Kerman in 2013". 436 nurses from selected hospitals in Tehran and Kerman were participated in this research by convenient sampling method. Data were collected using the Kanango Job Involvement Questionnaire. The score of 40 was determined as cut-off point for job involvement, and the relationship between job involvement and demographic characteristics in nurses was investigated. The results showed that most nurses were 31-40 years old. The mean score of job involvement was 36.07 ± 10.02 . Among the demographic characteristics, men had a higher job involvement than women, in terms of gender. Also, the job involvement score of nurses working in military hospitals was higher than non-military hospitals. In terms of other demographic characteristics, such as marital status, work experience, age, and education, there was no significant difference in terms of job involvement score. They came to the conclusion that due to the low score of job involvement, it is suggested that the effective factors and the motivations necessary to improve and increase nurses' job involvement be considered with regard to environmental variables (17).

Darwish et al carried out a research under the title "Relationship of Organizational Culture with Employees' job involvement in Khatam Al-Anbiya Hospital". The statistical population of this study was 1645 employees of Khatam Al-Anbiya Hospital in Tehran in 2014. The sample size determined by the Cochran formula was 312 people. The results showed a strong organizational culture and high job involvement in this hospital. There was a significant relationship between job involvement and different factors of organizational culture (except for dominant features). The researchers concluded that the individual, organizational and environmental variables affected the success and job involvement of the employees. Therefore, improving job involvement leads to more efficiency and facilitates the achievement of organizational goals by recognizing relevant variables such as organizational culture and cultural values. They also believe that managers should strive to improve the organization's performance by creating an appropriate space and strengthening organizational culture (18).

Ghaderi and Shamsi conducted a research entitled "Relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Job Involvement in Clinical Nurses". This research was performed as census on 180 nurses from different departments of the hospitals of Jiroft in 2012. To measure the level of emotional intelligence, the Bar-EQ standard questionnaire was used to measure occupational involvement. The standard questionnaire of emotional intelligence (EQ-i) was used for measuring emotional intelligence; for measuring the job involvement we applied the 10-item international standard questionnaire of Kanongo job involvement of which 81.1% of the samples were women. The mean age and mean work experience of the samples were 35.6 ± 8.18 and 26 ± 8.66 years, respectively. The mean scores of emotional intelligence and job involvement were 333.64 ± 33.63 and 40.81 ± 13.39 , respectively. Pearson correlation test showed a direct correlation (0.034) between emotional intelligence and job involvement. Based on the stepwise regression analysis, 9.6% of the changes in job involvement are related to the variables of emotional intelligence (19).

The final results showed that there is a direct relationship between emotional intelligence and job involvement; so they believed that the comprehensive planning in the field of growth and enhancement of emotional intelligence in nursing staff can lead to their personal and professional growth and this leads to an increase in Nurses' productivity and patient satisfaction, and ultimately improving the health of the society.

Riahi et al conducted a research entitled "Assessing Strategic Adaptation, Valuable Work, and Job Involvement (Staff Participation) at Hashemi Nejad Hospital in Tehran, 2012". The population under study consisted of 424 people of nursing, administrative, financial, support and paramedical occupational classes in Hashemi Nejad Hospital in Tehran. Out of this a sample size equal 202 persons were selected. Samples were selected by stratified random sampling and proportional to the number of population in each class. A questionnaire was used to collect data. A total of 172 employees participated in this research. Based on the findings, the mean scores and standard deviation of strategic adaptation and job involvement were 31.4 ± 4.47 from 40, that of valuable work was 32.42 ± 4.77 and that of job involvement 54.7 ± 19.34 from 70. They concluded in the end that all three of the variables under study represented a relatively favorable situation, and the goal-based management, allocation of posts and organizational occupations based on the type of employee's expertise and experiences, attention to their material and spiritual needs, and that the employees are allowed to supervise their work processes, they play a significant role in developing the capabilities of human resources staff and improving the status of the above variables (20).

Mir Hashemi et al carried out a research with the aim of "Investigating the relationship between emotional intelligence of emergency department nurses in Tehran hospitals and their job involvement". For this purpose, 230 nurses were selected and tested by multi-stage random sampling method. The analyses showed that there is a significant correlation between emotional intelligence and nurses' job involvement; based on the variables of emotional intelligence (self-awareness, self-management, social self-awareness and relationship management), a model can be provided to predict the variable of job involvement (21).

Zabani Shadbad conducted a research entitled "Role of Professional Ethics in Individual and Organizational Consequences." This study was performed on 290 employees of Tabriz University of medical sciences in the academic year of 2014-15. The sampling was carried out through a relative stratified random method and four questionnaires of professional ethics, job involvement, turnover and increasing efforts were used. The results of structural equation modeling showed that there is a positive causal relationship between professional ethics on the one hand and job involvement and increasing efforts on the other. Also, there was a negative causal

relationship between professional ethics and turnover. There was a positive causal relationship between job involvement and an incremental endeavor and a negative causal relation between job engagement and additive endeavor on the one hand and turnover. The findings also indicated that paying attention to professional ethics and promoting it among the employees of the organization would lead to job attachment and their involvement with their job as well as their incremental efforts (22).

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION:

With investigating 9 conducted researches in health educational centers affiliated with the Ministry of Health of Iran, this research has come to the conclusion that job involvement has direct and positive relationship with such variables as "Strategic Alignment", "Servant Leadership", "Transformational Leadership", "Demographic Characteristics", "Organizational Culture", "Strategic Alignment and Valuable Work", "Role of Professional Ethics" and "Emotional Intelligence". Therefore, it is necessary to strengthen it and other related variables in organizations.

Job involvement usually has relative stability over time. People with high Job involvement have, firstly, a better performance than others, as they are able to concentrate more on working aspects. Secondly, they are able to withstand work pressures due to their high power and the ability to withstand hardships. Ultimately, they experience a positive sense of working that can expand the range of their thought and action. It can also be said job involvement is a major factor in improving employees' attitude, behavior, performance and productivity. Managers can improve the performance of the organization through creating job involvement, and even achieve competitive advantage. When employees are involved in their jobs, they show positive behaviors, so in this way they provide their own interests and the interests of the organization. Involved employees, because of their high interest and passion for their work, tend to work beyond the expectations, and their performance will be better than those who do not have job involvement. Also, employees with a high job involvement will understand their work more meaningfully and more satisfactorily than others, while they will have more job satisfaction than others. As a result, it is possible to say that the higher the level of job involvement among employees of an organization, the more effective it will be. For this reason, in order to increase the level of job involvement, we need to look at the determinants of it in a realistic and comprehensive way. It seems that

high job involvement is an essential desirable characteristic of employees. Persons with high job involvement rarely think of leaving their job and it is expected they work for their organization for a predictable future. The job of employees with high job involvement, apparently, has a close relationship with many of their identities and their life goals, and it is very important to them.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This article is extracted from a research granted by Dezfoul University of Medical Sciences, Iran

REFERENCES:

1. Saadat E. Human Resource Management. Tehran. Samt. 2013.19 253-305.
2. Barekat G, Gilavand A. Evaluating the Relationship between Social Capital and Organizational Justice from the Perspective of Employees of Ahvaz Jundishapur University of Medical Sciences, in Southwest of Iran, *Espacios*, 2018; 39(8): 27-37.
3. Yamaguchi, I. The relationship among individual differences, needs and equity sensitivity. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 2003;18 (4), 324-344.
4. Gilavand A, Shooriabi M, Malakootian M. Investigating the Frequency of Occupational Exposure in Dentistry Students of Ahvaz Jundishapur University of Medical Sciences in Southwest of Iran. *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research*, 2018; 11(2): 1637-1642. 297-299. doi.org/10.22159/ajpcr.2018.v11i2.23191
5. Shooriabi M, Gilavand A, Emam SA. Evaluating the Participation Ratio of Dental Assistants Working in Dentistry Centers of the City of Ahvaz in Southwest Iran in Infection Control Educational Courses. *Der Pharmacia Lettre*. 2016; 8(16): 16-23
6. Gilavand A. The comparison of the tuition-paid and free tuition dental students' incentives in choosing their field of study at Ahvaz Jundishapur University of Medical Sciences, Southwest of Iran. *Ann Trop Med Public Health* 2017; 10(5): 1254-1259. doi: 10.4103/ATMPH.ATMPH_316_16.
7. Gilavand A. The Comparison of Iranian and Foreign Students' Motivations to Choose Dentistry Field of Study. *International Journal of Pediatrics*. 2016; 4 (6):1993-2010. doi: 10.22038/ijp.2016.6861
8. Shooriabi M, Gilavand A, Yazan M. Studying the Necessity for Presenting the Science of Determining

the Tooth shade Course in Educational Curriculum in Dentistry Faculties Based on the Evaluation of the Amount of Knowledge and Performance of General Dentists. *Der Pharmacia Lettre*. 2016; 8(13): 298-304.

9. Mehralizadeh Y., Gilavand A., Sheykhi alizadeh M., Hajizadeh K. Evaluation of the Health System Reform Plan In Iranian Universities of Medical Sciences in Terms of Community Empowerment: A Review, *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2017; 4(12): 4566-4579.
doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1119231

10. Coetzee, M., & de Villiers, M. Sources of job stress, work engagement and career orientations of employees in a South African financial institution. *Southern African Business Review*, 2010;14 (1), 24-58.

11. Mudrack PE. Job Involvement, Obsessive-compulsive Personality Traits, and Workaholic Behavioral Tendencies”, *Journal of Organizational Change Management* 2004; 17: 490-508.

12. Carson KD, Carson PP, Bedian AG. Development and construct validation of a career entrenchment measure. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology* 1995; 68: 301-320.

13. Brown SP. A meta-analysis and review of organizational research on job involvement. *Psychological Bulletin* 1996; 120: 235-255.

14. Gorjihasan A, Fatahi H, Kazemeini N, Shokri A. The Relationship between "Strategic Alignment" and "Employee Engagement" of Hasheminejad Hospital in Tehran. *teb*. 2017; 25 (2):107-118

15. Khalesi N, Salehi M, Moradi F, Ahadi nejad B, Mohamadi R, Rohani B. The Relationship between Servant Leadership and Job Involvement in Teaching

Hospitals Affiliated to Kurdistan University of Medical Sciences: 2011. *jha*. 2012; 15 (47):23-32

16. Bahrami M, Morvati M, Dehghan A, Montazeralfaraj R, Ahmadi G, Shahbazi H. The Relationship between dimensions of Transformational leadership and Job Involvement staff from managers View in teaching hospitals of Yazd in 2013. *TB*. 2016; 14 (6):554-565

17. Saeed Y, Tabanejad Z, Nehrir B, Ebadi A, Khoshab H, Babajani S. The relationship between job involvement and demographic characteristics in nurses in hospitals of Tehran and Kerman in 2013. *Journal of Clinical Nursing and Midwifery*. 2015; 3 (4):39-46.

18. Darvish H, Kolivand P, Kermani B. Relationship between Organizational Culture and the Involvement of Employees in the Khatam Alanbia Hospital in Tehran. *Shefaye Khatam*. 2014; 2 (S2):19-27

19. Ghaderi M, Shamsi A. The relationship between emotional intelligence and job involvement among hospital nurses. *Journal of Nursing Management*. 2013; 2(3): 8-15.

20. Riahi L, Baghbanian A, Fattahi H. Evaluating "Strategic Alignment", "Meaningful Work" and "Employee Engagement" of Tehran Hasheminejad Hospital in 2012. *JRUMS*. 2013; 12 (10):819-830.

21. Mirhashemi M, Sharifi H, Sabeti Sh. The relationship between emotional intelligence and job involvement among nurses. *ANDISHEH VA RAFTAR (APPLIED PSYCHOLOGY)*. 2008; 3 (9): 17-26.

22. Shadbad M, Hasani M, GhasemzadehAlishahi A. The role of professional ethics in individual and organizational consequences. *Medical Ethics Journal*. 2017; 40(11): 53-62.